

Heat Index Online Calculator

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Abstract

Air conditioning is one of the most important issues of Climate Justice. Air conditioning is the main electricity consumer in buildings equipped with air conditioning, while the waste for nothing is tens of percent or more. Overcooling below the Comfort Heat Index is not for comfort, actually it causes overcooling discomfort and a health hazard. The lower is the air conditioning temperature, the longer is its operation time.

Unlike many other GHG mitigation measures, setting the air conditioning to the Comfort Heat Index does not involve expenses or investment, on the contrary, it significantly reduces energy cost (mainly due to shorter operating time) and reduces investment in oversized air conditioning units.

The purpose of the Heat Index online calculator according to this work is to assist in setting the air conditioning unit to the correct temperature based on Comfort Heat Index.

The Heat Index online calculator according to this work can be found at:
<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/HI>.

Glossary

ΔE	overcooling air conditioning energy consumption for cooling and condense above baseline CHI, kWh thermal/year
$\Delta E\%$	overcooling energy, the ratio of actual energy consumption to baseline in CHI and OCAC, %
Δhr	overcooling hours, difference between actual cooling hours and comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC, hr/y
$\Delta hr\%$	overcooling hours, the ratio of actual cooling hours to comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC, %
ABS	absolute value of a number
Ave	average
AveHICdn	average Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours, °C
BL	baseline (for calculation of OverAC)
CHI	Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C (79.9°F)
Cool On	thermostat setting of air conditioning, °C
ECW	thermal energy for cooling and condense, kWh th/y
HI	temperature equivalent of the discomfort caused by the air temperature and the air relative humidity (RH), °C, (°F)
hrC	actual cooling hours, hr/y
hrCHI	cooling hours at CHI level, hr/y
OCAC	Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).
OCHI	Overcooling Heat Index - difference between the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and the actual Heat Index, °C
OverAC	Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning, multiplication of OCHI by operation hours below CHI (Δhr), dhr (degree-hours)
Ref	reference

RH	relative humidity of air, %
SQRT	square root value of a number
TF	room air temperature in degrees Fahrenheit

Units

Generally, this work is in metric units. Calculations and application of the Heat Index involve degrees Fahrenheit.

Heat Index – Air Humidity Temperature Equivalent

The Heat Index (HI) is the air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, °C (or °F).

Following is the official definition of the Heat Index as on the NOAA site [1]:

“The Heat Index is a measure of how hot it really feels when relative humidity is factored in with the actual air temperature. To find the Heat Index temperature, look at the Heat Index Chart above or check our Heat Index Calculator. As an example, if the air temperature is 96°F and the relative humidity is 65%, the heat index--how hot it feels--is 121°F. The red area without numbers indicates extreme danger.

Since heat index values were devised for shady, light wind conditions, exposure to full sunshine can increase heat index values by up to 15°F. Also, strong winds, particularly with very hot, dry air, can be extremely hazardous”.

Heat Index (HI) is calculated by “Nowagreen Heat Index and Overcooling Heat Index online calculator °C and °F “ [10] on site:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/Hi>

and by “Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization – BESOO v544 –

“Comfort Heat Index, cooling only, thermostatic control, outside walls layers temperature, infiltration, ventilation, thermal energy for cooling and condense” [9] on sites:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Heat Index Formula

Actually, the Heat Index (HI) is calculated not with a single formula but with a set of formulas. The original Heat Index formulas can be found on the website “NOAA - National Weather Service - Weather Prediction Center – The Heat Index Equation” [2].

The publication [2] includes the following recommendation regarding the order of application of the formulas:

“In practice, the simple formula (Steadman's Formula, in this work Formula 1) is computed first and the result averaged with the temperature. If this Heat Index value is 80 degrees F or higher, the full regression equation along with any adjustment as described is applied”.

Accordingly, the HI calculator described in this work applies the “simple formula” (Formula 1 as detailed below) as the first formula.

Formula 1 - Heat Index Steadman's formula (simple formula) for HI<80°F, °F

$$HI = 0.5 * (TF + 61.0 + 1.2*(TF - 68.0) + 0.094*RH)$$

Formula 2 - Heat Index Rothfus formula for HI=>80°F, °F

$$HI = -42.379 + 2.04901523 * TF + 10.14333127 * RH - 0.22475541 * TF * RH - 0.00683783 * TF * TF - 0.05481717 * RH * RH + 0.00122874 * TF * TF * RH + 0.00085282 * TF * RH * RH - 0.00000199 * TF * TF * RH * RH$$

Formula 3 - Correction for RH<13

if (RH<13 and TF>80 and TF<112) :

$$HI = HI - ((13 - RH) / 4) * \text{SQRT}((17 - \text{ABS}(TF - 95)) / 17)$$

Actually, in the Java programming language, this formula is split as follows:

```
var adj1 = (13 - RH) / 4;
var adj2 = Math.sqrt((17 - Math.abs(TF - 95)) / 17);
HI = HI - adj1 * adj2;
```

Formula 4 - Correction for RH>85

if (RH>85 and TF>80 and TF<87) :

$$HI = HI + ((RH - 85)/10) * ((87 - TF)/5)$$

<i>HI</i>	Heat Index – air humidity temperature equivalent, °F
<i>TF</i>	air temperature in Fahrenheit, °F
<i>RH</i>	air relative humidity in % (for humidity 60%, use number 60 and not 0.60)
<i>SQRT</i>	square root
<i>ABS</i>	absolute

(TF * TF) is applied instead of TF² and (RH * RH) instead of RH², as in the PHP programming language used for the BESOO simulation, the power function is somehow confusing.

Heat Index Online Calculators

This work uses the following Heat Index online calculators:

- **NOAA I:** NOAA - National Weather Service - General [3]
- **NOAA II:** NOAA - National Weather Service - Location [4]
- **ISG:** ISGlobal - The Barcelona Institute for Global Health [5]
- **calc:** Calculator.net - Heat Index Calculator [6]
- **NG:** HI calculator according to this work on nowagreen.ct.ws website [10]

Table 1 - Validation of correct application of the Heat Index formulas in the Heat Index online calculators, °C

Line #	Formula	°C	RH	NG	NOAA I	NOAA II	ISG	calc
Ref				[10]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
1	Formula 1	20.0	50	19.3611	19.4	N/A	19	19
2	Formula 1	26.6	50	26.6211		N/A	27	27
3	Formula 2	26.6	50	27.0542	27.1	N/A		
4	Formula 2	26.6	60	27.5939	27.6	N/A	28	28
5	Formula 2	31.0	100	49.0043	49.0	49.0	63	49
6	Formula 2	50.0	1	41.5877	41.6	41.6	43	42
7	Formula 2	50.0	100	206.1541	206.3	206.2	151	206
8	Formula 2	30.0	12	28.1319				
9	Formula 3	30.0	12	28.0367	28.1	28.1	28	28
10	Formula 2	30.0	1	28.4276				
11	Formula 3	30.0	1	27.2843	27.3	28.4	27	27
12	Formula 2	30.0	86	39.4475				
13	Formula 4	30.0	86	39.4586	39.5	39.4	38	39
14	Formula 2	28.0	100	35.6122				
15	Formula 4	28.0	100	36.3788	36.4	35.6	36	36

NOAA I [3] – 3 cases not correct – 70% correct

#3: the condition for Formula 2 is $HI \geq 80^{\circ}\text{C}$, however the condition applied is $HI > 79.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is not correct

#7: not correct result (corrected in NOAA II)

#9: disregarding Formula 3

NOAA II [4] – 7 cases not correct – 30% correct

#1-4: the calculator not applicable for air temperatures below 80°F , neglecting the overcooling discomfort

#9: disregarding Formula 3

#11: disregarding Formula 3

#13: disregarding Formula 4

#15: disregarding Formula 4

ISG [5] – 4 cases not correct – 60% correct

#: low resolution – rounded degree

#5: very big error in calculation: $HI = 63^{\circ}\text{C}$ instead of 49°C

#6: not correct result

#7: very big error in calculation: HI=151°C instead of 206°C

#13: not correct result

calc [6] = calculator.net – 100% correct

#: low resolution – rounded degree

Table 2 - Resolution of online Heat Index Calculators

NG [10]	NOAA I [3]	NOAA II [4]	ISG [5]	calc [6]
0.0001	0.1	0.1	0	0

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program - BESOO

This work is based on the Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program – BESOO version 544 as described in the publication “*Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning*” [9].

Version 544 is dedicated to cooling only, and the cooling is not limited in time.

The default ventilation in this simulation program is 7 changes per hour.

The integration interval is 10 seconds.

The BESOO Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization programs used for this work are available (free, no need to login) on:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Comfort Heat Index

Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is the Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling. Setting air conditioning systems to a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) provides air conditioning that is comfortable enough for those suffering from heat and much better for those suffering from air conditioning overcooling.

Cooling below the Comfort Heat Index not only wastes energy but also causes discomfort and health hazards for many people.

Comfort Heat Index (CHI) was first introduced in the publication “*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [7].

Table 1 - Air Conditioning Comfort Heat Index (CHI) [7]

Air Conditioning Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °F	79.9
Air Conditioning Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °C	26.6

Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI

Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) is the difference between the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and the actual Heat Index (HI).

Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI, was first introduced in the publication “*Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning*” [8].

Formula 5 - Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI, °C

$$OCHI = CHI - HI$$

OCHI	Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI, °C
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, °C
HI	Heat Index, °C

Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) is calculated by “*Nowagreen Heat Index and Overcooling Heat Index online calculator °C and °F* “ [10] on site:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/HI>

and by “*Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization – BESOO v544 – “Comfort Heat Index, cooling only, thermostatic control, outside walls layers temperature, infiltration, ventilation, thermal energy for cooling and condense”* [9] on sites:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Overcooling Heat Index, Energy, and Cooling Hours

Table 2 - Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), energy consumption (ECW), and cooling hours (hrC) - Jerusalem

Cool On °C	AveHICdn °C	OCHI °C	ECW kWh	ΔE%	hrC hr/y	Δhr%
16	15.06	11.54	8,004	871%	5,473	439%
17	16.16	10.44	7,270	782%	5,081	400%
18	17.24	9.36	6,495	688%	4,689	362%
19	18.32	8.28	5,697	591%	4,256	319%
20	19.38	7.22	4,823	485%	3,800	274%
21	20.42	6.18	3,818	363%	3,276	222%
22	21.46	5.14	2,884	250%	2,702	166%
23	22.51	4.09	2,108	156%	2,124	109%
24	23.56	3.04	1,482	80%	1,632	61%
25	24.61	1.99	990	20%	1,178	16%
OCAC						
25.4	25.02	1.58	824	0%	1,016	0%
Baseline	26.60	0.00	824		1,016	

Cool On	thermostat setting of air conditioning, °C
AveHICdn	average Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours, °C
OCHI	Overcooling Heat Index
ECW	thermal energy for cooling and condense, kWh th/y
ΔE%	overcooling energy, the ratio of actual energy consumption to baseline in CHI and OCAC, %
hrC	actual cooling hours, hr/y
Δhr%	overcooling hours, the ratio of actual cooling hours (hrC) to comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC (hrCHI), %

Table 3 - Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), energy consumption (ECW), and cooling hours (hrC) – Tel Aviv

Cool On °C	AveHICdn °C	OCHI °C	ECW kWh	ΔE%	hrC hr/y	Δhr%
16	15.44	11.16	12,200	206%	6,703	153%
17	16.54	10.06	11,337	184%	6,307	138%
18	17.64	8.96	10,461	162%	5,895	123%
19	18.75	7.85	9,574	140%	5,444	106%
20	19.85	6.75	8,713	118%	5,017	90%
21	20.96	5.64	7,865	97%	4,599	74%
22	22.06	4.54	7,007	76%	4,177	58%
23	23.16	3.44	6,139	54%	3,749	42%
24	24.26	2.34	5,309	33%	3,340	26%
25	25.35	1.25	4,497	13%	2,927	11%
OCAC						
25.6	26.01	0.59	3,990	0%	2,647	0%
Baseline	26.60	0.00	3,990		2,647	

Correlation between Overcooling Heat Index and Overcooling Period

The Nowagreen Heat Index calculator also indicates the increase in cooling hours with an increase of overcooling, applying a linear formula for parameter $\Delta hr\%/OCHI$. The calculator formula is a linear type, like:

$$y = ax + b$$

y $\Delta hr\%$ - overcooling hours, the ratio of actual cooling hours (hrC) to comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC (hrCHI)
 a, b coefficients of the linear formula
 x Overcooling Heat Index, $OCHI = CHI - HI$

Formula 6 - Coefficients of the linear formula

$$\Delta hr\% = a * OCHI + b$$

	a	b
Jerusalem $OCHI < 7.22$	0.0572463	-0.033795
Jerusalem $OCHI = > 7.22$	0	38.0%
Tel Aviv $OCHI < 7.22$	0.0087311	0.0737103
Tel Aviv $OCHI = > 7.22$	0	13.5%

The linear formula is conservative because it shows fewer overcooling hours than the actual.

Table 4 - Correlation between Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) and overcooling period ($\Delta hr\%$) - Jerusalem

Cool On	OCHI	$\Delta hr\%$	$\Delta hr\%$ to OCHI	Conservative Linear	Linear $\Delta hr\%$
$^{\circ}C$	$^{\circ}C$		$\%/^{\circ}C$	$\%/^{\circ}C$	
16	11.54	439%	38.0%	38.0%	439%
17	10.44	400%	38.3%	38.0%	397%
18	9.36	362%	38.6%	38.0%	356%
19	8.28	319%	38.5%	38.0%	315%
20	7.22	274%	38.0%	38.0%	274%
21	6.18	222%	36.0%	32.0%	198%
22	5.14	166%	32.3%	26.0%	134%
23	4.09	109%	26.7%	20.0%	82%
24	3.04	61%	19.9%	14.0%	43%
25	1.99	16%	8.0%	8.0%	16%

Chart 1 - Δ hr%/OCHI - Jerusalem

upper axis X = OCHI – Overcooling Heat Index, °C

lower axis X = Cool In – air conditioning operating temperature, °C

Table 5 - Correlation between Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) and overcooling period (Δ hr%) – Tel Aviv

Cool On °C	OCHI °C	Δ hr%	Δ hr% to OCHI %/°C	Conservative Linear %/°C	Linear Δ hr%
16	11.16	153%	13.7%	13.5%	151%
17	10.06	138%	13.7%	13.5%	136%
18	8.96	123%	13.7%	13.5%	121%
19	7.85	106%	13.5%	13.5%	106%
20	6.75	90%	13.3%	13.3%	90%
21	5.64	74%	13.1%	12.3%	69%
22	4.54	58%	12.7%	11.3%	51%
23	3.44	42%	12.1%	10.4%	36%
24	2.34	26%	11.2%	9.4%	22%
25	1.25	11%	8.5%	8.5%	11%

Chart 2 - $\Delta hr\%/OCHI$ – Tel Aviv

upper axis X = OCHI – Overcooling Heat Index, °C
 lower axis X = Cool In – air conditioning operating temperature, °C

Correlation between Overcooling Heat Index and Energy Consumption

Formula 7 - Coefficients of the linear formula

$$\Delta E\% = a * OCHI + b$$

	a	b
Jerusalem OCHI<7.22	0.10916785	-0.11600969
Jerusalem OCHI=>7.22	0	56.0%
Tel Aviv OCHI<7.22	0.01340185	0.08490182
Tel Aviv OCHI=>7.22	0	17.5%

The linear formula is conservative because it shows lower overcooling energy than the actual.

Table 6 - Correlation between Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) and overcooling energy ($\Delta E\%$) - Jerusalem

Cool On	OCHI	$\Delta E\%$	$\Delta E\%$ to OCHI	Conservative	Linear
°C	°C		%/°C	%/°C	$\Delta E\%$
16	11.54	871%	75.5%	56.0%	646%
17	10.44	782%	74.9%	56.0%	585%
18	9.36	688%	73.5%	56.0%	524%
19	8.28	591%	71.4%	56.0%	464%
20	7.22	485%	67.2%	56.0%	404%
21	6.18	363%	58.8%	55.9%	345%
22	5.14	250%	48.6%	44.5%	229%
23	4.09	156%	38.1%	33.0%	135%
24	3.04	80%	26.3%	21.6%	66%
25	1.99	20%	10.1%	10.1%	20%

Chart 3 - $\Delta E\%/OCHI$ - Jerusalem

Table 7 - Correlation between Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) and overcooling energy ($\Delta E\%$) – Tel Aviv

Cool On	OCHI	$\Delta E\%$	$\Delta E\%$ to OCHI	Conservative Linear	Linear $\Delta E\%$
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	$^{\circ}\text{C}$		$\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$	
16	11.16	206%	18.4%	17.5%	195%
17	10.06	184%	18.3%	17.5%	176%
18	8.96	162%	18.1%	17.5%	157%
19	7.85	140%	17.8%	17.5%	137%
20	6.75	118%	17.5%	17.5%	118%
21	5.64	97%	17.2%	16.0%	91%
22	4.54	76%	16.7%	14.6%	66%
23	3.44	54%	15.7%	13.1%	45%
24	2.34	33%	14.1%	11.6%	27%
25	1.25	13%	10.2%	10.2%	13%

Chart 4 - $\Delta E\%/OCHI$ – Tel Aviv

Calculator's Website

The Heat Index Calculator according to this work is available online (free, no need to login) on:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/Hi>

Chart 5 - Heat Index calculator according to this work on the website

Nowagreen Global Warming Database			
Heat Index and Overcooling Heat Index online calculator °C and °F			
change a number in any input field - all the rest will be done automatically			
	Set #1	Set #2	
Relative Humidity (RH) %:	<input type="text" value="60"/>	<input type="text" value="50"/>	
air temperature, °C:	<input type="text" value="16.00"/>	<input type="text" value="26.60"/>	
air temperature, °F:	<input type="text" value="60.80"/>	<input type="text" value="79.88"/>	
Heat Index °C:	15.2222	26.6211	
Heat Index °F:	59.4000	79.9180	
Air Conditioning overcooling discomfort			
<p>If Set #1 is related to the operating conditions of the air conditioner, the result is OVERCOOLING DISCOMFORT ! The Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is 26.6°C and the air conditioning Heat Index (HI) is 15.22°C, the Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) is 11.38°C. Such overcooling extends the cooling time by 432% in Jerusalem, 154% in Tel Aviv, average +293%, and causes energy waste of 637% in Jerusalem and 199% in Tel Aviv, average +418%.</p>			
<u>Air conditioning Comfort Heat Index</u>			
<p>Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is the Heat Index which is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling. Setting air conditioning systems to a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) provides air conditioning that is comfortable enough for those suffering from heat and much better for those suffering from air conditioning overcooling.</p>			
Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °C	<input type="text" value="26.6"/>		
Comfort Heat Index, °F	<input type="text" value="79.9"/>		
	Set #1	Set #2	
Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), °C	11.38		
Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), °F	20.48		

cite this page: <https://nowagreen.ct.ws/Hi>

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